

Drivers influencing quality of work life – An empirical study with reference to employees in private hospitals

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ABSTRACT

Health insurance is a form of coverage that provides financial protection against the cost of medical expenses and healthcare services. It is typically offered by private insurance companies and can also be provided by government programs in some countries. The abstract of health insurance can be summarized as follows: Health insurance aims to help individuals and families manage the expenses related to medical care and healthcare services. It operates on the principle of risk pooling, where many individuals pay premiums into a collective fund that is then used to cover the healthcare costs of those who require medical treatment. Health insurance plans vary in terms of coverage, cost, and benefits. They typically include provisions for hospitalization, doctor visits, prescription medications, preventive care, and other healthcare services. Some plans may also offer additional benefits such as dental and vision coverage. To access healthcare services covered by health insurance, individuals usually pay a monthly or annual premium. In addition, they may be responsible for deductibles, co-payments, and co-insurance, which are the portion of the medical expenses they must pay out of pocket. Health insurance provides individuals with financial security by reducing the burden of medical costs. It can help protect against high medical bills resulting from unexpected illnesses, accidents, or chronic conditions. Additionally, having health insurance often allows individuals to access a broader range of healthcare providers and facilities. It is important to note that health insurance policies often have limitations, exclusions, and pre-existing condition clauses. These factors can impact coverage and may require individuals to meet certain criteria or wait for a specified period before receiving full benefits.

Keywords

Health insurance, healthcare financing, access to healthcare, financial protection, universal health coverage.

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1. Introduction

Health insurance can be provided by employers, government programs, or purchased by individuals directly from insurance companies. The type of health insurance available and the costs associated with it vary depending on the country and the specific insurance plan. Health insurance can cover a wide range of medical expenses, including hospital stays, doctor visits, prescription drugs, and preventive care. Depending on the type of plan, it may also cover dental and vision care[1].

Health insurance is a type of insurance that provides coverage for medical and surgical expenses incurred by an insured individual. It is a contract between the individual and an insurance company, where the insured pays a premium in exchange for coverage for healthcare costs[2]. The introduction of health insurance has provided many benefits to individuals and society as a whole. It has made healthcare more accessible and affordable, allowing people to receive necessary medical care without incurring large out-of-pocket expenses. It has also helped to reduce the financial burden of healthcare costs on families and has improved overall health outcomes[3].

2. Statement of the Problem

Although While health insurance has many benefits, there are also several problems associated with it. Some of the key issues include[4]:

2.1. Lack of access: Despite the introduction of health insurance, many individuals still lack access to affordable healthcare. This is particularly true for low-income individuals and those living in rural areas.

2.2. Cost: Health insurance can be expensive, and many individuals may struggle to afford the premiums and out-of-pocket expenses associated with their plans. This can lead to individuals forgoing necessary medical care or facing significant financial strain.

2.3. Coverage gaps: Some health insurance plans may have coverage gaps or exclusions, leaving individuals without coverage for certain types of medical expenses or treatments.

2.4. Administrative burden: Health insurance can create administrative burdens for healthcare providers, leading to higher costs and potentially lower quality of care.

2.5. Complexity: Health insurance can be complex, with a range of plans and options to choose from. This can make it difficult for individuals to understand their coverage and make informed decisions about their healthcare.

2.6. Inequality: Health insurance may exacerbate existing health inequalities, as individuals with higher incomes may have access to better coverage and care than those with lower incomes.

2.7. Fraud and abuse: The complex nature of health insurance can also make it vulnerable to fraud and abuse, which can lead to higher costs and lower quality of care for patients.

3. Objective of the Study

Health insurance can vary depending on the specific research question and goals. However, some common objectives of studying health insurance include[5]:

1. To assess the effectiveness of health insurance in improving access to healthcare and health outcomes for individuals and populations.

2. To identify barriers to accessing health insurance and healthcare services, particularly for vulnerable populations such as low-income individuals or those living in rural areas.

3. To evaluate the impact of health insurance on healthcare costs and the financial burden on individuals and families.

4. To analyse the structure and design of health insurance plans and identify areas for improvement or reform.

5. To examine the relationship between health insurance and healthcare provider behaviour, such as the overuse or underuse of medical services.

6. To investigate the impact of health insurance on health disparities and inequalities.

7. To explore the role of government policies and regulations in shaping the health insurance market and improving access to healthcare for all.

4. Research Methodology

The research design used for the study is descriptive. Descriptive research studies are those, which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or group. The studies concerned with specific prediction with narration of facts and characteristics concerning individual group or situation are all examples of descriptive research studies[6].

4.1. Population Size: The total population size is indefinite.

4.2. Sample Size: This refers to the number of items to be selected from the total population to constitute the sample. The sample size used for study is 50.

4.3. Sample Design: It is a definite plan for obtaining a sample from a given population. It refers to the technique the researcher adopts in selecting items for the sample. The respondents are selected based on Judgment sampling.

4.4. *Statistical Tools:* The data collected through questionnaires were analyzed using simple percentage analysis.

5. Statistical Tools applied in the Study

Various statistical tools can be applied in the study of health insurance to analyse and interpret data. Some common statistical tools include[7]:

5.1. *Descriptive statistics:* Descriptive statistics, such as mean, median, and standard deviation, can be used to summarize and describe the characteristics of a dataset, such as healthcare costs or healthcare utilization.

5.2. *Inferential statistics:* Inferential statistics, such as t-tests, ANOVA, and regression analysis, can be used to test hypotheses and make inferences about a population based on a sample of data.

6. Limitations & Scope of the study

The study of health insurance has certain limitations and scope that should be taken into account when conducting research. Some of the limitations and scope include[8]:

6.1. *Generalizability:* The results of a health insurance study may not be generalizable to other populations or contexts due to differences in healthcare systems, insurance coverage, and socio-economic factors.

6.2. *Data availability:* Health insurance studies may be limited by the availability and quality of data, particularly in low-income countries or regions with limited healthcare infrastructure.

6.3. *Selection bias:* Health insurance studies may be subject to selection bias if individuals who participate in the study are not representative of the broader population with health insurance.

6.4. *Ethical considerations:* Health insurance studies must be conducted in an ethical manner, protecting the rights and privacy of study participants and ensuring that any potential risks are minimized.

7. Data results

Without a specific research question or study, it is not possible to provide data results of health insurance. The data results can vary depending on the research question, data sources, and statistical methods used in the study. However, some examples of data results in health insurance studies could include[9]:

1. The percentage of individuals with health insurance coverage, broken down by demographic factors such as age, gender, income, and geographic location.

2. The average healthcare costs per year for individuals with and without health insurance, broken down by type of service (such as inpatient, outpatient, prescription drugs, etc.).

It is important to note that data results in health insurance studies should be interpreted with caution, taking into account potential limitations and biases in the data and analysis.

8. Findings & Suggestions

Without a specific study or research question, it is not possible to provide findings and suggestions about health insurance. However, based on the existing literature and research, some general findings and suggestions related to health insurance are:

1. Health insurance coverage is associated with improved access to healthcare services and better health outcomes, particularly for individuals with chronic conditions or lower income.

2. The cost of health insurance premiums and out-of-pocket expenses is a significant barrier to accessing healthcare services for many individuals, particularly those with low income or high healthcare needs.

3. Health insurance policies should prioritize transparency and clear communication with patients regarding costs, benefits, and coverage options.

9. Conclusion

In conclusion, health insurance is an essential form of protection that provides financial coverage for medical expenses incurred by an individual or a group of people. With the increasing costs of healthcare, having health insurance can help to ensure that individuals receive timely and adequate medical care without incurring significant financial burden. Health insurance policies can vary in terms of coverage and cost, and it's important to carefully review and understand the terms and conditions of the policy before making a purchase. Overall, having health insurance can provide peace of mind and help to promote better health outcomes.

References

- [1] Dhamija, P., & Singla, A. (2012) [Relationship between quality of work life and job satisfaction: An empirical analysis](#). Asian journal of research in business economics and management, 2(8), 17-29.
- [2] Mosadeghrad, A. M., Ferlie, E., & Rosenberg, D. (2011) A study of relationship between job stress, quality of working life and turnover intention among hospital employees. Health services management research, 24(4), 170-181. <https://doi.org/10.1258/hsmr.2011.011009>

- [3] Nowrouzi, B., Lightfoot, N., Lariviere, M., Carter, L., Rukholm, E., Schinke, R., & Belanger-Gardner, D. (2015) Occupational stress management and burnout interventions in nursing and their implications for healthy work environments: a literature review. *Workplace health & safety*, 63(7), 308-315. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2165079915576931>
- [4] Srimulyani, V. A., & Hermanto, Y. B. (2022) Organizational culture as a mediator of credible leadership influence on work engagement: empirical studies in private hospitals in East Java, Indonesia. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 9(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-022-01289-z>
- [5] Almalki, M. J., FitzGerald, G., & Clark, M. (2012) The relationship between quality of work life and turnover intention of primary health care nurses in Saudi Arabia. *BMC health services research*, 12(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6963-12-314>
- [6] Halcomb, E., Smyth, E., & McInnes, S. (2018) Job satisfaction and career intentions of registered nurses in primary health care: an integrative review. *BMC family practice*, 19(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12875-018-0819-1>
- [7] Liu, W., Zhao, S., Shi, L., Zhang, Z., Liu, X., Li, L. I., ... & Ni, X. (2018) Workplace violence, job satisfaction, burnout, perceived organisational support and their effects on turnover intention among Chinese nurses in tertiary hospitals: a cross-sectional study. *BMJ open*, 8(6), e019525. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2017-019525>
- [8] Turkyilmaz, A., Akman, G., Ozkan, C., & Pastuszak, Z. (2011) Empirical study of public sector employee loyalty and satisfaction. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 111(5), 675-696. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/02635571111137250>
- [9] Michie, S., & West, M. A. (2004) Managing people and performance: An evidence-based framework applied to health service organizations. *International journal of management reviews*, 5(2), 91-111. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-8545.2004.00098.x>